

Enhanced Plant Disease Detection Model Using Yolov10 with De-Hazing and Histogram Equalization

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Abstract

Disease threatens farmers by reducing crop yield and global food availability. Plant disease detection models had been deployed to mitigate these challenges, but poor image quality due to environmental factors and low-quality devices affects the accuracy of the approaches. This study enhances disease detection using YOLOV-10 with de-hazing and histogram equalization techniques. Maize and cassava plants were selected for primary data collection, yielding 2,141 images (1,024 maize, 1,117 cassava). The PlantVillage dataset provided 54,303 images across nine plant classes, totalling 56,444 images. De-hazing and histogram equalization improved the YOLOV-10 model for better detection accuracy. Performance evaluation over 200 epochs used precision, recall, bounding box loss, and distribution focus loss metrics. The model achieved a bounding box loss of 0.3, a precision of 0.91 (indicating minimal false detections), and a recall approaching 1, confirming its ability to detect diseased plants accurately. With 94% accuracy, it outperformed many reviewed models.

Keywords: *Plant Disease, Image Classification, De-haze, Histogram Equalization, YoloV-10*

Introduction

In Plant diseases caused by fungi, viruses, and microorganisms result in significant crop losses annually (Syed *et al.*, 2022). Traditional detection methods are prone to error, delay, and high costs (Buja *et al.*, 2021; Ruparelia *et al.*, 2022; Yadhav *et al.*, 2020). Poor image quality can negatively affect the classification process's result. Recent studies have explored AI and deep learning for plant disease detection (Ebere *et al.*, 2024; Nnaedozie *et al.*, 2023). Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) architectures have achieved high accuracies in plant disease identification (Saleem *et al.*, 2019; Singh *et al.*, 2023; Sun *et al.*, 2022). However, existing methods may not have given due attention to the interfering impact of the environment on the plants.

When data from farms are directly fed to the traditional model, it might not be reliable for the accurate classification of plant diseases. One of the major conditions that contribute to this problem is poor weather conditions such as humidity, fog, dust, or rain. These may be clogged on the plant leaves or data acquisition system (camera) and hence present a poor-quality data collection problem.

The major contributions of this study are:

- i. A new data model with localized plant diseases in Nigeria
- ii. An enhanced deep-learning algorithm for improved plant disease classification

Problem statement

Related Works

A summary of the literature was presented in Table 1, considering the most recent and closest works, and then making findings to establish the research gap.

Table 1: Summarized review of related works

Authors	Approach	Accuracy	Gap
Akshay and Yerigeri (2022)	CNN	94.80%	Result not in real-time
Long <i>et al.</i> (2022)	DL networks	97.05%	Need third-party interference
Ramakrishna <i>et al.</i> (2019)	ML, CNN architectures	96%	Delay problem
Haile (2019)	ANN	97.6%	Limited to two plants
Kaur <i>et al.</i> (2019)	GoogleNet	97.82%	suffer delay in real-time problem
Adedoja <i>et al.</i> (2023)	NASNet -Mobile DL	99.31%	The occlusion problem was not addressed
Bangal <i>et al.</i> (2022)	CNN	91.41%	Result needs improvement

Mohameth <i>et al.</i> (2020)	DL, SVM, KNN	99.53%	Disease diversity not considered
Sundari <i>et al.</i> (2023)	CNN	100%, 99.2%	Limited user diversity
Akshai <i>et al.</i> (2021)	CNN	98.27%	CNN delays in real-time problem
Mohanty <i>et al.</i> (2020)	DL	99.35%	Limited application diversity

Materials and Methods

This section provides a detailed overview of dataset acquisition, preparation, integration, proposed model architectures, and operations.

Data collection, preparation and integration

The dataset was collected from primary and secondary sources, focusing on maize and cassava plants. Primary data came from the Enugu State Ministry of Agriculture (maize) and the Enugu State Agricultural Development Program (cassava). Diseases considered include mosaic virus, yellow curl virus, bacterial spot, early blight, late blight, and molds. The primary dataset consists of 2,141 annotated images prepared in Roboflow. The secondary data source, the PlantVillage dataset, includes 54,303 images across nine plant classes with 14 disease types. In total, the dataset comprises 56,444 images. Figure 2 shows the data distribution in the Roboflow environment.

Figure 1: Data annotation and labelling environment in Roboflow

Figure 1 displays the data annotation tool in Roboflow. Captured images were imported, and bounding boxes were assigned for classification. Each annotated image was then labelled based on disease type or healthy condition.

Figure 2: Distribution of the prepared plant diseases dataset.

Figure 2 shows a distribution of the images in the dataset. These images represent different characteristics of plant behaviour with different conditions and form the training, test, and validation dataset for this work.

The New System and Sub-systems

This section presents the new system and sub-system components, explaining how they were used for the development of the new farm disease detection system. Figure 3 presents the system and sub-system diagram.

Figure 3: System and sub-system diagram of the farm disease detection model

Data Processing

Processing used an equalized de-hazing model combining a dehaze algorithm and histogram equalization. The dehaze algorithm, based on scattering (He *et al.*, 2020) and dark colour channel models (Li *et al.*, 2022), improved image clarity. Histogram equalization enhanced image quality and restored edges blurred during processing.

YOLOV-10, Model of benchmark

The transfer learning algorithm of this work is the YOLOV-10. Figure 3 presents the traditional YOLOV-10 architecture, which is made of three main sections - the backbone, neck, and the predictor.

Figure 3: Architecture of traditional YOLOV-10 (Akhmedov *et al.*, 2024)

The De-Haze model

The Dehaze model used in this work combined the atmospheric scattering model and dark colour channel prior model to determine the transmission map of the haze pixels and then refined with a guided filter. The atmospheric scattering model assumed that observed image $I(x)$ combines the scene $J(x)$, transmission map $t(x)$, and atmospheric light (A) as shown in Algorithm 1 (He *et al.*, 2020).

Algorithm 1

1. Start
2. Estimate atmospheric light A :

$$A = \max(I(x))$$

3. Estimate transmission map $t(x)$ with dark colour channel prior

$$t(x) = 1 - w \cdot \min\left(\frac{J_{dark}(x)}{A}\right)$$

4. Refine transmission map $t(x)$ using guided filter

$$q(x) = \text{guided}_{filter}(I, t)$$

5. Recover the scene $J(x)$

$$J(x) = \frac{I(x) - A}{q(x)} + A$$

6. End

Post-processing techniques using histogram-oriented gradients approach.

Existing algorithms remove haze but struggle with detail restoration and colour balance, reducing contrast and obscuring disease indicators (Qu et al., 2024; Xu et al., 2024; Li et al., 2024). The Histogram Equalization Approach (HEA) (Wang et al., 2024) enhances dehazed images for accurate classification

Algorithm 2: Histogram Equalization (HE)

1. Start
2. Image representation as $M \times N$
3. Compute histogram using the intensity of images
4. Normalize the histogram and compute the cumulative distribution function
5. Map intensities with equation 4.8
6. Generate output as S_x
7. End

The equalized dehazed algorithm is shown below.

Algorithm 3: Equalized Dehaze

1. Start
2. Estimate atmospheric light A :

$$A = \max(I(x))$$

3. Estimate transmission map $t(x)$ with dark colour channel prior

$$t(x) = 1 - w \cdot \min\left(\frac{J_{dark}(x)}{A}\right)$$

4. Refine transmission map $t(x)$ using guided filter

$$q(x) = \text{guided}_{filter}(I, t)$$

5. Recover the scene $J(x)$

$$J(x) = \frac{I(x) - A}{q(x)} + A$$

6. Normalized $p(x) = \frac{n_x}{n} = \frac{1}{n} \quad \begin{matrix} n \\ (I_i = x) \\ i = 1 \end{matrix}$

7. Map intensity $S_x = \text{round} \left((L - 1) \frac{pj}{x} \right)$

8. Generate new output as $J_{final}(x) = S_x(J(x))$

9. End

The improved YOLOV-10 Model

The enhanced YOLOV-10 model integrates an equalized dehazed algorithm with traditional YOLOV-10, enhancing image processing for farm-captured plant images. (Figures 4 & 5)

Figure 4: The Equalized dehazed block diagram

Figure 5: Architecture of enhanced YOLOV-10

Post-processing

Performance evaluation metrics

The performance evaluation metrics for the model are Precision (P), Recall (R), mean average precision (*mAP*), and average precision (*AP_i*), as shown in equation 3.1 - 3.4.

$$P = \frac{TP}{TP+FP} \tag{3.1}$$

$$R = \frac{TP}{TP+FN} \tag{3.2}$$

$$AP_i = \int_0^1 P(R)d(R) \tag{3.3}$$

$$mAP = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N AP_i \tag{3.4}$$

Where TP is True Positive plant disease detection, FP is Negative samples that are Positively detected, FN are Negative samples that are Not detected.

Results and Discussion

The plant disease dataset was divided into training (80%), testing (10%), and validation (10%) sets. The trained model was then tested, validated, and converged to generate the plant disease detection model.

YOLOV-10 Training Performance Evaluation

This section evaluates the YOLOV-10 training performance using metrics such as mean average precision (mAP), loss, recall, precision, and F1 score. The training process involved:

1. Splitting data into training, test, and validation sets
2. Training YOLOV-10 for 149 epochs

Each epoch yielded unique results, modelling the YOLOV-10's performance in learning disease patterns in plants.

Figure 6: Training data losses

Figure 7: Validation losses

Figure 8: Result of the precision, recall, and mAP

Training Result

The training results are presented, evaluating the model's performance using various metrics.

Training Losses

Training losses decreased (Figure 6), indicating:

- Improved boundary detection (bounding box loss)
- Enhanced disease classification (classification loss)
- Better focus on plant images (focal loss)

Validation Losses

In Figure 7: Validation losses decreased steadily for Bounding box, Classification, and Focal loss. Indicating minimal loss in detection and focusing accuracy

Evaluation Metrics

- Precision: 0.91, indicating few false detections.
- Recall: steadily increased to near 1, indicating correct detection of all plant data.
- mAP50-95: effective detection quality at higher Intersection Over Unit (IOU) thresholds. (figure 8)

The enhanced YOLOV-10-based plant disease detection model demonstrated effectiveness in correctly classifying plants with diseases and healthy plants with a high success rate.

Discussion

Figures 6 - 8 present the result of the model training. Figure 6 shows the training result of the model considering the bounding box, classification, and Focal loss.

- Bounding box loss decreased steadily, improving boundary detection accuracy (Figure 6, left)
- Classification loss reduced, indicating the correct classification of plant diseases within detected bounding boxes (Figure 6, centre)
- Focal loss performance improved, enhancing bounding box focus on plant images (Figure 6, right)

After 200 epoch iterations, bounding box loss reached 0.3, indicating good model performance

The three validation graphs in Figure 7 (val/box loss, val/class loss, and val/df_l_loss) show steady decreases, indicating:

- Minimal classification loss
- Improved bounding box detection accuracy
- Enhanced focusing quality for plant images

Overall, these results suggest strong model performance

Precision metrics ensured accurate disease classification, minimizing false positives. The model achieved a precision of 0.91, indicating minimal false detections.

Recall measured correctly classified positive instances, steadily increasing to nearly 1. This suggests the model effectively detected almost all plant diseases by the end of training.

The mean average precision (mAP50-95) evaluated detection across IOU thresholds (50%-95%), confirming strong performance at higher IOUs. Overall, the YOLOV-10-based model effectively classified diseased and healthy plants on farms with high accuracy

YOLOV-10 model for plant disease detection

A comparative analysis was conducted to validate the plant disease detection model against existing models in the literature (Table 6)

Table 6: Comparative analysis of plant disease detection models

Authors	Year	Approach	Dataset	Accuracy (%)
Adedoja <i>et al.</i>	2022	NASNet-Mobile DL	-	99.31
Akshai <i>et al.</i>	2021	CNN	Plant Village	98.27
Akshay and Yerigeri	2022	CNN	Sample images	94.80
Alirezazadeh <i>et al.</i>	2023	Attention mechanism	DiaMOS plant	86.89
Alirezazadeh <i>et al.</i>	2023	Convolutional Block Attention Module (CBAM) + EfficientNetB0	Plant Village	86.89
Bangal <i>et al.</i>	2022	CNN	Kaggle	91.41
Benfenati, <i>et al.</i>	2023	Autoencoder Clustering approach	Plant village	89 76
Haile	2019	ANN	Maize, Potato	97.6
Kaur <i>et al.</i>	2019	GoogleNet	Public database	97.82
Long <i>et al.</i>	2022	DL networks	Field and glasshouse images	97.05
Mohanty <i>et al.</i>	2020	DL	Public dataset	99.35
Our model	2024	Equalized –YOLOV-10	Plant village	94

Ramakrishna et al.	2019	ML, CNN architectures	Plant Village	96
Sundari et al.	2023	CNN	Plant Village, pathology dataset	100, 99.2

Our model competes favourably with existing models in the literature, demonstrating reliable performance. This is attributed to the integration of the equalized dehazed algorithm, enhancing its effectiveness in real-world applications.

Conclusion

To address crop disease detection, which threatens yield and food security, an enhanced image classification approach was developed. A new data model integrated localized maize and cassava disease images with the PlantVillage dataset. To improve accuracy, an advanced YOLOV-10 model was enhanced with dehaze modelling and histogram equalization. The trained Equalized YOLOV-10 model effectively detected plant diseases.

This study mitigated poor data quality and improved detection by integrating these techniques within YOLOV-10. It also addressed application diversity by focusing on Nigerian crops. Key contributions include an equalized dehaze algorithm for optimized image processing and an enhanced YOLOV-10 model for improved classification. The results confirm its effectiveness in detecting plant diseases with high accuracy.

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